
India's Role in Myanmar's Transition into Democracy

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ABSTRACT

India is well known in the world as the largest democratic country. India's democratic culture has been giving special importance to certain issues so that the foundation of democracy can be further strengthened such as - people's participation, rule of law, tolerance, equality of all religions, castes, races, genders, etc. Not only that, India is equally respectful in building the foundation of democracy in its neighboring countries. Because the foundation of democracy in India's neighboring countries is very shaky. Especially in Myanmar, the country has been under military rule for a long time due to repeated military coups. Pro-democracy activists have faced active movements there at various times to restore democracy, where India has an important role. India's approach to Myanmar's democratic restoration has been characterized by a balance between pragmatic engagement and support for democratic processes. Historically, India condemned the suppression of democracy following Myanmar's military coup in 1988 and supported pro-democracy movements. However, in the early 1990s, India shifted its policy to engage with Myanmar's military junta, driven by strategic and security considerations, including concerns over insurgencies along their shared border and China's growing influence in the region.

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Introduction

India and Myanmar share a colonial past, as both were part of British India until 1937. This historical connection laid the foundation for strong cultural and political ties. India supported Myanmar during its independence struggle, and later, during its early years as a republic. However, the military coup in 1962 strained relations, as Myanmar turned inward and India became more vocal about democratic governance. Basically, if we look at the democratic history of Myanmar, we see that Myanmar's journey towards democracy has been tumultuous, marked by colonial rule, military coups, pro-democracy uprisings, and a struggle for civilian governance. As the world's largest democracy, India has played a pivotal role in supporting Myanmar's complex transition to democracy, a process marked by periods of military rule, civil unrest, and reforms. India's approach, shaped by its "Act East" policy, has focused on balancing pragmatic geopolitical interests with its commitment to democratic values. This has involved engaging with Myanmar's political leadership, providing development assistance, and supporting democratic institutions, all while navigating the challenges posed by regional instability, ethnic conflicts, and China's growing influence in Myanmar. As a result, India's role in Myanmar's democratic transition is both a reflection of its foreign policy priorities and a testament to its aspiration to be a stabilizing force in Southeast Asia. India and Myanmar share deep cultural, religious, and historical ties, particularly due to the shared Buddhist heritage. Democracy in Myanmar aligns with India's vision of promoting shared values of pluralism, secularism, and peaceful coexistence in the region. As the world's largest democracy, India has a moral and political responsibility to support democratic movements in its neighborhood. Promoting democracy in Myanmar also aligns with India's global image as a champion of democratic ideals.

So, in this study I would like to discuss with three main objectives:

Firstly; to highlight India's strategic interests in supporting the democratic restoration in Myanmar.

Secondly; to discuss India's major initiative towards democratic transition in Myanmar.

Thirdly; focused on major challenges to India in this perspective

India's Interests in Supporting Democratic Restoration Process in Myanmar

India's strategic interests lie in supporting democracy in its neighbourhood, according to Dr. S. D. Muni, Professor Emeritus at Jawaharlal Nehru University and a former ambassador. He believes that while

efforts to impose democracy pro-actively may fail, when a society is ready, it is essential to support and encourage democracy. Muni spoke at a national seminar on India's External Democracy Support, stating that India has supported democratic movements selectively when it is in its interests. He emphasized that India has played a critical role in South Asia's transformation into a democratic space, and emphasized the importance of supporting inclusive democracy. He emphasized the need for India to avoid majoritarian rule, as it undermines inclusive democracy. Muni emphasized the importance of improving India's democracy to encourage its neighbours to follow suit (Revi, 15 June, 2019). India's Foreign Secretary Vinay Mohan Kwatra urged Myanmar to return to federal democracy amid escalating conflict between armed resistance groups and Myanmar military in Chin, Shan, and Sagaing provinces (Bhattacharjee, December 06, 2023). India's Foreign Minister Mr. Jaishankar also brought up the illegal drug traffic, the arms trade, and the actions of rebel groups along the Indo-Myanmar border during a meeting with U Than Shwe, and assured that India supports the restoration of democracy in Myanmar (NDTV, July 11, 2024).

India has a vested interest in promoting and supporting democracy in Myanmar due to several strategic, political, and economic reasons, and balancing its commitment to democratic values with regional security and economic concerns.

1. Strategic Concern:

- **Stability in the Indo-Myanmar border Region:**

India shares a 1643 km-long porous border with Myanmar, covering the north-eastern states of Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland, Manipur, and Mizoram. This border region plays a crucial role in India's national security due to insurgency threats, cross-border crimes, and strategic interests. This region has been affected by insurgent groups like NSCN-K (National Socialist Council of Nagaland Khaplang), ULFA (United Liberation Front of Assam), and PLA (People's Liberation Army of Manipur). These groups often use Myanmar's dense forests as safe havens to launch attacks on Indian security forces. Not only that, various non-traditional security threats like arms smuggling, drug trafficking (Golden Triangle region), and human trafficking are prevalent due to the porous nature of the border. Myanmar's instability enables these criminal networks to thrive. Political instability in Myanmar especially after the 2021 military coup, has led to an influx of refugees, particularly from the Chin community into Mizoram. This migration poses security and humanitarian challenges. A democratic Myanmar is likely

to ensure political stability, and it fosters stronger bilateral security ties with India, leading institutionalized border management, such as the India-Myanmar Regional Border Committee meetings (Ministry of External Affairs, 2020-21). India and Myanmar have historically cooperated in operations against insurgent groups like the NSCN-K and PLA. A democratic government is more inclined to uphold such agreements, ensuring sustained counter-insurgency efforts.

- **Countering China's Influence:**

Myanmar's strategic location between India, China, and Southeast Asia makes it a key geopolitical player. A democratic Myanmar that maintains balanced foreign relations can help India counter China's growing influence in the region. Particularly, Aung San Suu Kyi led civilian government in Myanmar have sought to reduce overdependence on China by engaging with other powers, including India, ASEAN, Japan, and the West.

2. Economic Interests:

India's economic interests in Myanmar are encompassing trade, investment, infrastructure development, and energy cooperation. As of 2019-2020, India was Myanmar's fifth-largest trading partner, with exports from India to Myanmar totalling approximately \$ 973.89 million and imports from Myanmar amounting to 547.25 million (Rajeshwar, 2022). India has been actively involved in developing infrastructure projects in Myanmar to enhance connectivity and facilitate trade. The Kaladan Multimodal Transit Transport Project is a significant initiative aimed at connecting the Indian seaport of Kolkata to Sittwe port in Myanmar, and further linking to Mizoram in India via road. This project is expected to provide an alternative route to India's north-eastern states, reducing dependence on the Siliguri Corridor. (Roche, 14 August, 2014). Additionally, the India-Myanmar Thailand Trilateral Highway project seeks to establish a 3,200 km triangular highway connecting the three countries, enhancing regional connectivity and economic integration (Ministry of External Affairs, December 20, 2018). Energy cooperation is another critical area of India's economic interest in Myanmar. India has explored the potential of Myanmar as a source of natural gas, with companies like ONGC and GAIL holding stakes in oil and gas exploration projects (Price, June, 2013). A stable and democratic Myanmar is critical for the timely completion and functioning of these projects. As well as Myanmar serves as India's gateway to ASEAN under its Act East Policy. A democratic government would likely foster stronger bilateral ties and trade partnerships.

India's Role in Restoration of democratic process in Myanmar:

India has played a cautious but constructive role in supporting the restoration of democracy in Myanmar. Balancing its strategic interests, regional security concerns, and commitment to democratic ideals, India's role in Myanmar's democratic transition can be analyzed through the following key aspects:

1. Diplomatic engagement:

India has consistently advocated for dialogue and reconciliation between Myanmar's military (Tatmadaw) and pro-democracy groups, including the National League for Democracy (NLD) led by Aung San Suu Kyi. It supports an inclusive political process that respects the will of the Myanmar people. India has raised concerns about Myanmar's political situation in international forums, such as the United Nations, while avoiding direct criticism to maintain its strategic relationship. However, in September 2024, India extended an unprecedented invitation to Myanmar's anti-junta political and military forces to attend a seminar in New Delhi. This seminar, focusing on "Constitutionalism and Federalism" marked a significant shift in India's foreign policy, indicating a more inclusive approach to supporting Myanmar's democratic restoration (Lone & Ghosal, September 23, 2024).

2. Supporting through ASEAN

India has supported ASEAN-led initiatives, such as the Five-Point Consensus on Myanmar, which calls for an immediate cessation of violence, dialogue among all stakeholders, and humanitarian assistance. By aligning itself with ASEAN's regional approach, India ensures that its actions are part of a broader collective effort to restore democracy in Myanmar (The Economic Times, 19 June, 2021).

3. Humanitarian Assistance

India has extended humanitarian aid to the people of Myanmar, especially during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. This aid is aimed at building goodwill and supporting the citizens, even amidst political turmoil. India has refrained from taking a hardline approach, instead focusing on minimizing the humanitarian impact of Myanmar's political crisis, particularly in the border regions.

4. Providing a Platform for Dialogue

India has maintained open channels of communication with both Myanmar's military leadership and pro-democracy forces. This balanced approach allows India to act as a potential mediator in fostering democratic dialogue while protecting its strategic interests.

5. Security and Border Management

India has continued to collaborate with Myanmar's authorities on border management, insurgency control, and counter-terrorism efforts, while subtly encouraging the restoration of civilian governance. By maintaining a working relationship with the military, India ensures that security and stability along its northeastern borders are not jeopardized, and India has invested in capacity-building programs for Myanmar's institutions, including training officials, promoting educational exchanges, and supporting civil society initiatives. Programs under the India-Myanmar Friendship Project aim to enhance democratic governance by empowering local communities and building institutional capacity.

6. Balancing Strategic Interests

India has avoided outright condemnation of the military coup to prevent Myanmar from moving closer to China, which already wields significant influence in the country. This cautious diplomacy ensures India retains leverage in Myanmar while quietly advocating for democratic principles. By engaging with all stakeholders, India maintains its influence in Myanmar's infrastructure projects, such as the Kaladan Multimodal Project and India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway, crucial for India's Act East Policy.

7. Engagement with Myanmar Diaspora

India has supported the democratic aspirations of Myanmar's diaspora, including pro-democracy activists, without openly interfering in Myanmar's internal affairs. Cultural and religious ties, especially through shared Buddhist heritage, have been leveraged to promote India's goodwill among the people of Myanmar.

Challenges to India's Role in Democratic Restoration in Myanmar

India's efforts to support the restoration of democracy in Myanmar are influenced by a complex interplay of strategic, security, and economic considerations. It faced various challenges in that case such as the ongoing civil war in Myanmar poses significant security risks for India, particularly along the 1643 km Indo-Myanmar border. Incidents such as the January 2023 bombings by Myanmar's armed forces near Mizoram underscore the potential for violence to spill over into Indian Territory. Additionally, the influx of refugees sharing ethnic ties with communities in Northeast India present challenges related to resources allocation, public health, and potential increases in smuggling activities (Kushwaha, April 24, 2023). Myanmar's deep ties with China also complicate India's efforts to push for democratic reforms without risking its strategic and security interests. The Myanmar military's entrenched power limits India's ability to influence domestic politics. India's handling of the Rohingya refugee issue has drawn criticism and poses a challenge to its pro-democracy stance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, while India supports democracy in Myanmar, its approach is pragmatic, balancing idealism with strategic and security concerns. A democratic Myanmar is not just beneficial for regional peace but also for India's long-term strategic goals in Southeast Asia.

India's role in the restoration of democracy in Myanmar reflects a fine balance between realism and idealism. While it advocates for a democratic transition, India prioritizes stability and regional security. By engaging diplomatically with all stakeholders, supporting ASEAN-led initiatives, and providing humanitarian assistance, India seeks to promote democracy without compromising its strategic interests. India's Foreign Minister Pranab Mukherjee said that: "We have strategic and economic interests to protect in Burma. It is up to the Burmese people to struggle for democracy, it is their issue" (Bhaumik, 26 September, 2007).

In recent years, India's stance has been nuanced. Following the 2021 military coup in Myanmar, India refrained from outright condemnation, opting instead for continued engagement with the junta. This approach was influenced by India's strategic interests, such as the country's 1,000-mile border, which it prefers not to become hostile with. The border areas of Myanmar are allegedly used by separatist groups like the National Socialist Council of Nagaland (NSCN) to stage attacks in India. India's military may be

concerned that the Chin National Defense Force may inspire a resurgence of a Naga independence movement. Additionally, India has economic interests in maintaining cordial relations with Myanmar's military, as Myanmar has natural resources useful for India's high-tech industry and the restoration of a stable central government is vital for India's Kaladan Multimodal Transit Transport Project and the Trilateral Highway Project which are vital for enhancing regional connectivity. Myanmar's military may be willing to provide India greater access to these resources if India continues to provide weapons and opposes calls for sanctions on the SAC (Martin, 22 November, 2021). Despite maintaining ties with Myanmar's military leadership, India has also shown support for democratic forces. In September 2024, the Indian Council of World Affairs (ICWA) extended an unprecedented invitation to Myanmar's anti-junta political and military forces to attend a seminar in New Delhi. This move marked a significant shift in India's foreign policy, signaling its willingness to engage with pro-democracy factions (Lone & Ghosal, 23 September, 2024).

Furthermore, India's Foreign Minister, Subrahmanyam Jaishankar, has expressed deep concern over the ongoing violence and instability in Myanmar. In meetings with Myanmar's officials, he emphasized the negative impact on the border region and stressed the necessity of protecting India's infrastructure projects in Myanmar. He also advocated for an early return to democratic governance in the country (Reuters, 26 June, 2024). In summary, India's role in Myanmar's democratic restoration involves a delicate balance between engaging with the military junta to safeguard its strategic interests and supporting democratic processes to promote regional stability.

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